
Correction of Cubitus Varus with Lateral Closed Wedge Osteotomy and Cross K-Wire Fixation

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Issue Details

Issue Title: Issue 1

Received: 15 January, 2021

Accepted: 08 February, 2021

Published: 31 March, 2021

Pages: 3557 - 3565

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Abstract

Objective:

In children the occurrence of arm injury is frequent as they have immature skeletal. Malunion of supracondylar fractures often leads to cubitus varus, or "gunstock deformity." Various corrective osteotomies have been described for the correction of cubitus varus. A study was conducted for evaluation of good results in patients after lateral closed wedge osteotomy with cross K wire Fixation.

Methods & Materials:

Lateral closed wedge osteotomy was performed on nineteen children having cubitus varus due to malunion, which was fixed using Cross K-wire. Evaluation of patients was done for carrying angle, elbow range of motion radiological correction of humeroulnar angle and complications, if any. Before osteotomy procedure application to calculate amount of deformity humeroulnar angle was drawn on X-rays by intersection of the long axis of the humerus and ulna. In the two patients having anterior bony bump, bumpectomy was also done to improve flexion.

Results:

All patients were healed by 8 weeks and K-wires were removed without any anesthesia. One patient had inadequate correction. Superficial pin tract infections were developed in two patients which was cured successfully by oral antibiotics and pin tract dressings. No neurovascular complications occurred. There was no loss of correction or pin loosening. Sixteen patients had excellent result, whereas three patients had fair result as per Bellmore's criteria.

Conclusion:

It is not necessary to apply Complex three-dimensional osteotomy for cubitus varus correction. With proper planning and execution simple lateral closed wedge osteotomy cross K-wires (cross kirschner wire) fixation can give good results.

Keywords

Cross K-wire, cubitus varus, deformity, lateral closed wedge osteotomy, malunion supracondylar humerus

1. Introduction:

Cubitus varus is most commonly observed in children and people with immature skeletal growth. Cubitus varus (bow elbow), commonly known as Gunstock deformity occurs due to abnormal healing i.e malunion of supracondylar fracture of the upper arm bone or humerus.

Malunion can occur due to;

1. Inadequately treated or untreated fracture,
2. Loss of reduction in patients treated with cast due to inadequate reduction or improper cast application,
3. Inadequate fixation in surgically treated patients
4. Impaction of medial column leading to late collapse into varus.

This complication of supracondylar fractures had a frequency of 30 % cases however this percentage has decreased with operative treatments. Cubitus varus can unlikely cause any functional disability or deformity which occurs rarely. The occurrence of cubitus varus is seen in only extension type of supracondylar fracture of the humerus which can cause loss or complete reduction of carrying angle. This kind of injury is most commonly occurs in the children from the age group 5 to 7 years.

Although it doesn't cause functional disability initially but if left untreated it can lead to various kind of consequences for example secondary fractures, lateral instability and nerve palsies.

The severity of a cubitus varus deformity is graded as follows:

1. Grade I - loss of physiologic valgus
2. Grade II - varus of 0 to 10 degrees
3. Grade III - varus of 11 to 20 degrees
4. Grade IV - varus >20 degrees

It can be corrected with corrective osteotomy of the humerus and internal or external fixation of the bone until union. Lateral closed wedge osteotomy is considered to be preferred procedure to correct the bow-elbow deformity, complications can be minimized with appropriate stabilization with the help of plate and screw.

Following three components are the constituents of deformity

1. Coronal malalignment with varus: It does not remodel and requires corrective osteotomy to restore the carrying angle
2. Hyperextension: It occurs in the plane of elbow movements, it can remodel to some extent in younger children <10 years, and hence, its correction may not be necessary.
3. Internal rotational deformity: It is well compensated by shoulder joint movements and therefore does not cause significant functional limitation and usually does not require correction

Although the major indication for surgery of cubitus varus deformity is cosmetic correction of the unsightly deformity, few studies with long-term follow-up of patients with cubitus varus have shown that these patients may face problems such as increased chances of lateral humeral condyle fractures, poster lateral instability of the elbow, and tardy ulnar nerve palsy.

Various types of osteotomies have been reported in literature with no consensus on the ideal modality. Complex three-dimensional osteotomies have been described advocating correction of all three components of the deformity. However these osteotomies are technically difficult to perform. We conducted this study to evaluate whether a simple lateral closed wedge osteotomy can give predictably good results. The aims and objectives of the study were to assess the functional and radiological outcome of patients who underwent cubitus varus deformity correction with a simple lateral closed wedge osteotomy and also to evaluate whether fixation of osteotomy with cross K-wires construct is strong enough to maintain correction till osteotomy unites. In the present prospective study, we are presenting results of 19 cases of posttraumatic cubitus varus deformity treated with this technique.

2. Methods & Materials

After taking approval from the institutional ethics committee and consent taken from the patients, a study was conducted between May 2012 and December 2017 among . Nineteen cases, including 14 males and 5 females, of posttraumatic cubitus varus deformity caused by malunion of supracondylar fracture humerus in children upon them corrective osteotomy was performed. growth disturbance were ruled out as cause of deformity after waiting at least 1 year to perform the operative procedures. The average age of subjected patients were almost 8.5 years at the time of corrective procedure.

Clinical evaluation of all patients was done before surgery. Carrying angle and range of motion of affected and normal side were recorded. Before osteotomy procedure application to calculate amount of deformity humeroulnar angle was drawn on X-rays by intersection of the long axis of the humerus and ulna.

2.1 Operative Procedures

Patients were given proper anesthesia and tourniquet was applied they were positioned supine. The lower end of the upper arm bone was exposed. Under IITV guidance , the osteotomy site was marked and K-wires were passed according to template done on preoperative X-Ray. Two percutaneous K-wires, one each from lateral and medial side of the distal humerus, were passed up to the distal osteotomy site for stabilization. The osteotomy was done by making multiple drill holes along the guide wires and completing it with osteotomes. In patients who had significant hyperextension, anterior cortex of proximal segment was cut off to create an oblique osteotomy surface to achieve correction of the hyperextension deformity. The desired wedge of bone was removed, the osteotomy gap was closed, and the predrilled stabilization K-wires were advanced, crossing above the osteotomy site and engaging the opposite cortex, thus giving a cross K-wire fixation [Figure 1]. In the two patients having anterior bony bump, bumpectomy was also done to improve flexion. Wound was closed in layers, and above-elbow plaster slab was applied.

Figure 1: (a) Preoperative X-ray of normal side (b) preoperative X-ray of affected side showing calculation of deformity by humeroulnar angle and templating of wedge (c and d) postoperative X-rays showing correction of deformity (e-h) intraoperative IITV images showing surgical steps

3. Results

Follow up of patients were done at 2, 4, 6, 8, and 12 weeks and afterwards at every 3 monthly intervals till 1 year. Osteotomy wounds took 8 weeks to heal. The K-wires were removed in OPD after healing. No anesthesia was used this time. Postoperative stiffness was not observed in any patient. Elbow flexion was significantly improved after bumentomy in the two patients. Superficial pin tract infection was developed in two patients who were cured successfully by oral antibiotics and pin tract dressings. Pin loosening, deep infections and loss of fixation was not observed. Patient did not develop any neurovascular complications. Excellent results were showed in all patients except one who had in adequate correction with a rectus. Average 17 degree varus was improved to average 8 degree valgus

Table 1: Clinical Details of Patients

Age	Gender	Preoperative Carrying Angle		Postoperative Carrying angle		ROM (Range of motion)		Follow-up	Time to Union (weeks)	Result
		Normal	Affected Side	Immediate Postoperative	At 12 Weeks	Preoperative	Postoperative 1 year			
9 years 2 Months	Male	8	30	6	6	-20_80	-5_125	2 Years 6 months	6	Excellent
6 Years	Male	8	15	8	8	-5_130	0_130	3 years	4	Excellent
7 Years 3 Months	Male	9	12	8	8	-01_30	0_130	2 Years 6 months	4	Excellent
13 years	Female	12	20	10	10	-10_120	-5_120	1 year	8	Good
8 years 2 Months	Male	7	30	5	5	-15_85	0_130	5 years 6 Months	6	Excellent
10 years 6 Months	Male	10	14	10	10	-15_120	-5_135	2 Years 6 months	6	Excellent
9 Years	Male	13	20	12	12	-10_130	-10_130	1 year	6	Excellent
8 Years 3 Months	Male	9	14	8	8	-10_115	-5_125	2 years	6	Good
7 Years 6 Months	Female	12	16	9	9	-20_110	0_130	3 years	4	Excellent
6 Years	Male	8	10	8	8	-10_20	0_135	3 years	4	Excellent
8 Years 10 Months	Female	11	15	10	10	0_130	0_130	2 years	6	Excellent
11 Years 3 months	Male	10	13	10	10	-10_115	-10_115	1 Year	8	Excellent
7 years 1 Month	Male	8	25	0	0	-5_130	0_135	2 Years	4	Good
8 Years	Male	9	14	7	7	-10_120	-5_125	1 year	6	Excellent
6Years 4 Months	Male	6	13	5	5	-5_130	0_135	1 year 6 Months	4	Excellent
12 years 1 months	Female	15	14	13	13	-10_120	-10_120	1 Year 6 months	8	Excellent
9 Years	Female	12	12	11	11	0_130	0_130	1 Year	6	Excellent
7 Years 8 Months	Male	10	16	7	7	-25_110	0_135	1 Year	4	Excellent
10 Years 6 Months	Male	8	25	5	5	-10_130	-5_130	1 year	6	Excellent

All patients were declared asymptomatic after completion of one year. as per Bellmore's table 16 patients had excellent results and three patients had fair results.

Table 2: Bellemore's Criteria

Outcome	Difference between ROM on Normal and affected side	Difference between carrying angle on Normal and affected side	complications
Excellent	Difference < 10 degrees	< 5	None
Good	Difference 10-20	6-10	Minor
Poor	Difference > 20	>10	Residual effect/revision surgery
* Range of Motion			

4. Discussion:

Malunion is the usual cause of supracondylar fractures of the humerus which lead to cubitus varus deformity. It commonly occurs in children. Historically cubitus varus was considered a cosmetic deformity initially but later on various problems did occur in the patients and were reported by many authors. Davids first reported six cases of lateral condylar fracture of the humerus in children with preexisting cubitus varus due to malunited extension-type supracondylar fractures of the humerus. Takahara reported nine patients with distal humeral fractures complicating varus deformity. O'Driscoll reported 24 patients of cubitus varus deformity who developed tardy posterolateral instability of the elbow 2–3 decades later. These patients presented with lateral elbow pain and recurrent instability. With cubitus varus, the mechanical axis, the olecranon, and the triceps line of pull are all displaced medially. The repetitive external rotation torque on the ulna permitted by these deformities can stretch the lateral collateral ligament complex and lead to posterolateral rotatory instability. Tardy ulnar nerve palsy has also been associated with cubitus varus, and Ogino in 1986 was the first to report cubital tunnel syndrome due to cubitus varus deformity. With cubitus varus deformity, the olecranon fossa moves to the ulnar side of the distal humerus and the triceps shifts a bit ulnar ward. It has been theorized that this ulnar shift might compress the ulnar nerve against the medial epicondyle, narrowing the cubital tunnel and resulting in chronic neuropathy. Abe reported 15 patients with tardy ulnar nerve palsy caused by cubitus varus deformity with a mean interval of 15 years between the trauma and onset of symptoms. A fibrous band running between the heads of the flexor carpi ulnaris was thought to cause ulnar nerve compression.

It has been observed from various literatures that cubitus varus is not such a benign deformity as was once considered and that surgical correction should be offered to patients with significant deformity.

Corrective osteotomy is an optional procedure but it is considered to be the most successful one in reduction of symptoms and recurrence of cubitus varus deformity. The aim of the osteotomy is to correct the alignment of the elbow joint to a normal range of 5 to 15 degrees, as well as create a stable joint. There are various osteotomy techniques including

1. lateral closing wedge
2. French osteotomy
3. Modified French osteotomy
4. Medial opening wedge
5. Step cut
6. Oblique
7. Dome
8. Pentalateral

However, no one technique is safer or more successful over others. Besides, it is uncertain whether the correction of axial rotational malunion is necessary to achieve

better outcomes, as the carrying angle was not influenced by the degree of uncorrected torsional deformity in one study. This observation is important since attempts at correction through axial derotation often render the osteotomy site unstable from reduced cortical contact. However, the long-term consequences of uncorrected rotational malunion after corrective osteotomy are unknown. Pins, screws, staple, and tension band constructs with wires are typically used for internal fixation of the osteotomy in the pediatric population, as hardware prominence is not uncommon in this age group.

Since the deformity is a combination of varus, hyperextension, and internal rotation, many surgeons have suggested and voted for complex three-dimensional osteotomies to correct all the components of the deformity. Two groups of patients were compared by Takagi, the first group underwent three-dimensional osteotomy, whereas the second group only underwent coronal plane correction. They concluded that for osteotomies to correct cubitus varus deformity, correction of internal rotation is not needed. In fact they found that there was more loss of correction in the first group because rotation reduced the area of bone contact. They also found that children younger than 10 years showed remodeling of hyperextension on the final follow-up and concluded that in patients under 10 years of age, surgical correction of hyperextension is not needed when correcting the varus deformity.

Medial, posterior, and lateral approaches are used for performing these corrective osteotomies. Medial approach requires ulnar nerve dissection and a graft in case of open wedge osteotomy. Posterior approach, although gives better exposure, may lead to loss of terminal flexion due to scarring of triceps and posterior soft tissues. Lateral exposure is easy and gives sufficient exposure for correction without the disadvantages of the previous two approaches lateral closing wedge osteotomy was chosen as it is a simple procedure with predictably good results. An issue of Lateral condylar prominence occurs in applying lateral closing wedge osteotomy; but, in younger children this prominence is remodeled.

Various authors have described various methods for stabilization of the osteotomy – K-wires, screws, screws with tension band, plates, and external fixator. Although plates are considered to best stabilized preferred modality of fixation in older children however cross K-wire construct gave sufficient stability without any fixation loss in any of patients. A big advantage of K-wires was that it dint require anesthesia or any other surgery to be removed after healing of osteotomy.

5. Conclusion

It is not necessary to apply Complex three-dimensional osteotomy for cubitus varus correction .With proper planning and execution simple lateral closed wedge osteotomy cross K-wires fixation can give good results.This technique is simple and gives preferably stable results of osteotomy and with the help of Cross K-wire fixation it can be stabilized, moreover external implant can be easily removed without anesthesia and does not require another surgery.Hence it can be concluded that

Lateral close wedge (LCW) osteotomy along with cross K-wire fixation is the easiest, safest and inherently stable method of correction for cubitus varus occurring due to malunion of supracondylar fractures of the humerus.

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